

STScI SPACE TELESCOPE SCIENCE INSTITUTE

DUST OBSCURED NUCLEAR SUPERNOVAE REVEALED BY SPITZER

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NGC 1672

Supernova rates serve as an important probe of star formation models and initial mass functions. Optical ground-based surveys typically discover nearly 3-10 Xs fewer SNe than predicted due to high dust extinction in the nuclear regions of star forming galaxies. A successful SN survey in the local universe must be conducted at longer wavelengths and with a space-based telescope, which has a stable PSF to reduce the necessity for any subtraction algorithms and thus residuals. Here, we report on a 2-yr *Spitzer*/IRAC 3.6 μ m survey for dust-extinguished SNe in the nuclear regions of forty luminous infrared galaxies (LIRGs) within 200 Mpc. The asymmetric *Spitzer* PSF results in worse than expected subtraction residuals when implementing standard template subtraction. Forward-modelling techniques improve our sensitivity by ~ 1.5 mag. We report the detection of nine SNe, five of which were not discovered by optical surveys. After adjusting our predicted rates to account for the sensitivity of our survey, we find that the number of detections is consistent with the models. While this search is none the less hampered by a difficult-to-model PSF and the relatively poor resolution of *Spitzer*, it will benefit from future missions, such as *Roman*, with higher resolution and more symmetric PSFs.

NGC 6296

MISSING SN PROBLEM

The ability to detect all SNe in a survey limits the completeness of any rate study. This is particularly true in galaxies with high star-formation rates, where gas and dust obscure most of the SNe. In fact, visible-wavelength surveys for SNe in dusty starburst galaxies have established SN rates that are unexpectedly similar to rates observed in more normal galaxies.

Observed HST SN rates (Strolger+15) compared to predictions from the UV/optical SFRs (Madau & Dickinson) and FIR SFRs (Chary & Elbaz), Strolger et al. (2015) link the low CCSNr (and the subsequent source of discrepancy between the UV/optical and IR-derived SFRs) to dust obscuration,

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The effects of dust on the intensity and shape of a blackbody spectrum. The plotted flux is scaled relative to the peak flux at $A_V = 0$ mag. Since more absorption occurs at shorter wavelengths, the peak of the blackbody spectrum shifts beyond the near-infrared (i.e., 2.1 μ m) as A_V increases > 25 . For these extinction levels, *Spitzer*/IRAC Channel 1 (3.6 μ m) provides an optimal window for detecting SNe.

FORWARD MODELING

Despite the absence of atmospheric effects when working with images taken by space telescopes, there are three features of the *Spitzer* data that combine to make precise galaxy subtraction difficult. Forward modelling infers an analytic galaxy model on the sky by tracing the light ('forward') through convolution with the PSF and pixel, and then sampling by the detector (Rubin+21).

Fox+21

Comparison of sample data products, in this case for the first epoch of NGC 6240, used in our transient search. Top left: Original, unsubtracted MOPEX processed data. Top right: Standard alignment and subtraction of two epochs. Bottom left: Forward modeling subtraction, where the circle corresponds to our forward modelling radius. Bottom right: Subtraction of two epochs that have been forward modelled, but in this case are spaced nearly one year apart so that the telescope roll angle is similar. The color scale and stretch is constant for all subtracted images shown in this figure. The point source is SN 2013dc. It is present in all the images, but is most clearly detected in the bottom right. The central source is the galaxy nucleus. As described in the text, there are a number of caveats for modeling the inner core, including non-linearity concerns. Correcting those issues is beyond the scope of this paper, but we account for them in our statistics.

FIVE DUST EXTINGUISHED SNE DISCOVERED

We detect nine SNe, five of which were NOT discovered by optical surveys.

Fox+21

Press Release Graphic of REAL data

SURVEY SENSITIVITY, INTERPRETING RATES, AND FUTURE WITH ROMAN

The expected rate can be calculated from the following equation: $CCSNr = \frac{2.7 L_{IR}}{10^{10} L_{\odot}} (100 \text{ yr}^{-1})$. To properly compare the observed number of SNe detected to the predicted value, we first have to correct for the number of expected SNe to account for our decreased sensitivity in the nuclear regions due to poor subtraction residuals. We also need to take into account our empirical sensitivity limit (~ 17.5 , shown in the figure below). These restrictions limit a significant fraction of the each galaxy in which we can search for and detect a SN. The large number of galaxies observed, however, compensates for these inefficiencies and provides adequate statistics. In total, we predict 14 ± 6 SNe, and discover 9 SNe. We conclude that our observations are generally consistent with the predictions, especially when considering counting statistics ($\sigma = \text{sqrt}(14) = 3.7$). While this search is none the less hampered by a difficult-to-model PSF and the relatively poor resolution of *Spitzer*, it will benefit from future missions, such as *Roman* and *JWST*, with higher resolution and more symmetric PSFs.

Absolute magnitudes of the nine SNe discovered in our sample (green symbols). The photometry corresponds to zero host galaxy extinction for all the events and therefore their absolute magnitudes should be considered as lower limits. Also plotted are early (i.e. <3 month) photometry from Szalai et al. (2019) of nearby (<50 Mpc) SNe II-P and some SNe Ia within 30 d of explosion (black and red symbols, respectively). Dashed, dotted, and dotted-dashed lines represent apparent brightness levels of 17, 18, and 19mag, respectively. We are sensitive down to ~ 17.5 mag.

Fox+21

The 3.6 μ m light curves of the four detected known transients in our Survey (with black symbols), together with previously published light curves (grey symbols and shaded colored regions, adopted from Szalai et al. 2019). Dark-grey transparent rectangles mark the single epoch of photometry for the other five detected sources within the possible periods (taking into account the dates of last non-detections). Widths and heights of the rectangles denote the uncertainties of epochs and absolute magnitudes of the five previously unknown transients, respectively.

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